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A Study on Investment Pattern of Home Makers-With Special Reference to Palayamkottai Region

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Abstract: Financial investment is an asset that you put money into hope that it will grow or appreciate into larger sum of money. If investment is effective then it would also increase the productivity capacity of the economy. Investment made in different sectors is the most important determinant for the growth of the economy. The investment needs of the public and private sector are partly met out by the flow of fund from general public and partly met out by government tax revenue contributed by general public. Economic growth of a nation is determined by savings and its transformation into investment. Households are the biggest contributors and their savings is equal to 23% of India's GDP. From ancient time, women have been managing home. Therefore they are called "Home Makers". As the name suggests the present research has been done to know the awareness level of home makers and their preferences and consideration for investing money. Now a day's investing money has become a very complex task because there are huge number of investment companies. The rules and regulations, terms and conditions of investments are very complex. The objective of the study was to determine the relationship between income and investment pattern among the respondents. The study was conducted among home makers. Though the home makers don't have direct income of their own, they are able to save a minimum of 5% to 10% from their house hold saving. The data was collected by distributing a structured questionnaire to 175 respondents. Convenience sampling was used for the purpose of data collection. This study also focused on the effects of demonetization in the investment pattern of home makers.

Keywords: Investment awareness, pattern of investment of home makers, effects of demonetization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Investments are made both by men and women. But in last two decades there is an increase in number of women, who have capabilities to save and invest. As research studies in the field of investment pattern of women have remained limited, an attempt has been made to study the investment pattern of home makers in the present work. Investment made in different sectors is the most important factor for the growth of the economy. Both private and public sector investment needs are largely satisfied by the flow of funds from the general public. In case of public sector, its investment needs are partly met out of government's tax revenue contributed by general public. Women want to save a portion of their current income to meet the future needs such as constructing a house, marriage of children, unexpected contingencies.

Household savings take two forms, financial savings and physical savings. Financial savings include currency, bank deposits, shares and debentures, life insurance, provident and pension funds etc. Physical savings are in the form of construction of houses, purchase of flats, household equipments etc.

Importance of Investment for Women

"Save for a rainy day" goes a wise old saying. In those days saving is given importance, but today investment is given more importance than savings.

Saving is a part of your income that you put away regularly, it does not necessarily provide returns and it can only meet your short-term needs. Investing on the other hand, provides returns and helps you grow your capital, which in turn, will help you fulfill your financial goals.

Here are five reasons that will change the way you think and make you more determined to invest:

➤ Be prepared for emergencies

A sudden medical emergency or unemployment can cause a financial crisis. For instance, do you have the means to provide for your family if you were hit by unforeseen circumstances such as an illness that makes you unable to work, or an accident that immobilizes you? Investing helps you create a financial cushion for your family. Ideally you should have investments to the extent of at least six months' income at all times. Debt-oriented Unit Linked Insurance Plans (ULIPs) will help you accumulate the funds you need for this purpose.

➤ Financial security

Your financial security depends on how much you invest and how efficiently you do so. Investments can help you build a corpus so that you can generate a large cash reserve. A large cash reserve means

no anxiety about your financial security and more empowerment. Investing regularly in equity-oriented ULIPs over the long term has the potential to help you build a sizeable corpus to fulfill this purpose.

➤ **Fulfilling financial goals**

Buying your own home, or a bigger home, buying a new car, your children's education and their marriage are some goals that are important to you. To fulfill these goals, you need the right type of investment plans. Depending on when the financial goal will come up for fulfillment, you can select investment-oriented insurance plans. For goals that will arise in the near future (say 5-7 years hence) debt-oriented or balanced ULIPs would be suitable.

➤ **Wealth creation**

In order to create wealth you need investment options that add an element of growth to your money. Equity-oriented ULIPs have the potential to help you build your wealth kitty over an investment horizon of 7-10 years and beyond.

➤ **Fighting inflation**

Inflation eats away at your savings. With each passing year, prices keep rising. Investments help you protect your capital against price rise. A good way to beat inflation is to park your money in investments that offer returns that are higher than the rate of inflation.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of related literature is an important step in undertaking research. It helps in clarifying and defining the problem, stating objectives, formulating hypotheses, selecting appropriate design and methodology of research as well as interpreting the results in the light of the research work already undertaken.

Gnana Desigan.C (2006) in their study entitled "Women Investors Perception towards Investment – An Empirical Study" identified the women investors investment pattern, influencing factors, risk preference level and problems of women investors in Erode town. The findings of the study reveal that, women investors prefer to invest in bank deposits and jewels, they are influenced by safety and liquidity and the problems faced by them are cumbersome procedure and formalities, commission and brokerage.

P.Geetha (2009) in her article titled "A Study on the Choice of Investment Avenues of Individual Investors at Tirunelveli District" observed that Investment is the employment of funds on assets with the aim of earning income or capital appreciation. Therefore, the study concludes that the investment behaviors of the respondents are frequently changing. The highly preferred investments by the respondents are bank deposits, postal savings and insurance.

Dr. Aparna Samudra and Dr. M. A. Burghate (2012) in their article "A Study on Investment Behavior of Middle Class Households in Nagpur" identifies that bank deposits remain the most popular instrument of investment followed by insurance where post office savings deposits are the third preferred investment option. Thus from the study, it was found that most of the investors invest in bank Deposits.

Bhushan (2014) To examine the awareness level and investment behaviour of salaried individuals towards financial products. The study concludes that the respondents are quite aware and park their money in traditional and safe financial products whereas awareness level of new age financial products among the population is low

Prof. Patil Sonali, Dr. Nandanwar Kalpana(2015) in their study " Review of literature on individual investment behavior" identifies that the individual investors buying behavior is influenced by various factors such as social, economical, psychological, and demographic. Individual investor's investments are backed by benefits and money. Individual investors still prefer to invest in financial products which give risk free return. The study also confirmed that Indian investors prefer to play safe in the market. The financial regulators have to organize seminars, programs for creating awareness and boost confidence level among the investors.

Research Design

- The study is a descriptive survey study.
- Primary data is collected through self structured questionnaire
- Secondary data is collected from existing reports, books, journals & magazines and websites.
- The sample size of the study was 150 respondents and they were selected from palayamkottai at random according to the convenience.
- Statistical tools like percentage analysis, likert scale methods were used.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the role of home makers in making investment decisions.
- To know the investment avenues that the home makers usually prefer.
- To find out whether the home makers are looking for long term growth or return.
- To examine the awareness level and effects of demonetization in the investment pattern of the home makers.

III. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Table 5.1: Demographic Profile

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Up to 25 years	20	13%
	25 to 30 years	28	19%
	30 to 35 years	35	23%
	Above 35 years	67	45%
Educational Qualification	12 th	63	42%
	UG	32	21%
	PG	19	13%
	others	36	24%
Nature of family	Joint family	79	53%
	Nuclear family	71	47%
Size of family	Less than 3	15	10%
	3 to 5	113	75%
	5 to 7	15	10%
	More than 7	7	5%
Nature of residence	Own house	98	65%
	Rental house	42	28%
	Lease house	10	7%
Family income per month	Up to Rs 10000	55	37%
	Rs 10000 to Rs 20000	63	42%
	Rs 20000 to Rs 30000	28	18%
	More than Rs 30000	4	3%

Source: Data collected through Questionnaire

From the above table 5.1 it is inferred that

- 45 percent of the respondents are above 35 years.
- 42 percent of the respondents are 12th qualified..
- 47 Percent of the respondents are from nuclear family.
- 75 percent of the respondents have 3 to 5 members in their family.
- 65 percent of the respondents reside at their own house.
- Majority (42 percent) of the respondents have a monthly income of Rs 10000 to Rs 20000.

Table 5.2 Investment profile

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Experience in investment	Less than 2 years	31	20%
	2 to 4years	60	40%
	4 to 6 years	49	33%
	More than 6 years	10	7%
Investment decision	Myself	25	17%
	Husband	80	53%
	In laws	30	20%
	Children	15	10%
Amount of investment per month	Less than Rs 1000	40	27%
	Rs 1000 to Rs 3000	73	49%
	Rs 3000 to Rs 5000	17	11%
	More than Rs 5000	20	13%
Motive of investment	Short term profit seeking	56	37%
	Steady income	17	11%
	Long term profit seeking	50	33%
	other	27	19%
Frequency of investment	Daily	9	6%
	Monthly	113	75%
	Quarterly	10	7%
	annually	18	12%
Mode of investment	Direct	118	79%

	Through agent	32	21%
(If direct) source of investment	News paper	40	34%
	T.V	30	25%
	Internet	18	15%
	Friends & peer investors	20	17%
	Own analysis	10	9%
Demonetization affect investment	Yes	68	45%
	No	82	55%
Preference in investment after demonetization	Bank	75	50%
	Gold	37	25%
	Real estate	12	8%
	Private chit fund	26	17%

Source: Data collected from Questionnaire

From the above table 5.1 it is inferred that

- Majority of the respondents have the investment experience of 2 to 4 years.
- Majority of the respondents says that the investment decisions are taken by their husband.
- Majority of the respondents have a monthly investment of Rs 1000 to Rs 3000.
- Majority of the respondents invest for short term profit.
- Majority of the respondents invest directly.
- Majority of the respondents choose news paper as a source of investment.
- Majority of the respondent says that demonetization does not affect their investment pattern.
- Majority of the respondent prefer to invest in bank after this demonetization.

Table: 5.3 Preference of the investors

Likert scaling method is used to analyze the preference and the reason of investment by the respondents.

S.no	Factors	Weighted score	average score	Rank
1	Saving account in bank	654	130.8	I
2	FD account in bank	510	102	IV
3	Govt securities	610	122	IV
4	Post office saving account	619	123.8	III
5	L I C	502	100.4	VII
6	Mutual fund	484	96	VIII
7	Shares	470	94	IX
8	Gold & silver	632	126.4	II
9	Real estates	600	120	V
10	Private chit fund	420	84	X

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table 5.3 shows that majority of the respondents prefer to invest in saving account in bank, followed by the investment in gold and silver and post office saving account.

Reasons for investment

Table 5.4a Calculation of Garrett Value

Rank	Percent position Value =100(Rij - 0.5)/No of rank	Garrett value
I	100 (1- 0.5)/6 = 8.3	77
II	100 (2- 0.5)/6 = 25	63
III	100 (3 -0.5)/6 = 41.6	54
IV	100 (4 -0.5)/6 = 58.3	46
V	100 (5 -0.5)/6 = 75	37
VI	100 (6 -0.5)/6 = 91.6	23

Table 5.4b Garrett Ranking

Factors	I (77)	II (83)	III (54)	IV (46)	V (37)	VI (23)	No. of respo	Score	Avg. Score	Rank
1. For reducing tax liability	82 (6314)	32 (2014)	14 (756)	10 (460)	8 (296)	4 (92)	150	9932	66.2	II
2. For medical expenditure	80 (6140)	38 (2344)	7 (378)	10 (460)	6 (222)	9 (207)	150	9821	65.47	III
3. For maintaining status in the society	70 (5340)	40 (2520)	8 (432)	10 (460)	12 (444)	10 (230)	150	9476	63.17	V
4. For compulsion of agent	40 (3080)	44 (2772)	10 (540)	28 (1288)	20 (740)	8 (184)	150	8604	57.36	VI
5. For safety measures	48 (7546)	30 (1890)	10 (540)	4 (184)	6 (222)	2 (46)	150	10428	69.52	I
6. For education purpose	80 (6160)	28 (1764)	8 (432)	14 (644)	10 (370)	10 (230)	150	9600	64	IV

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

- Garrett ranking method is used to analyze the reasons for investment.
- The above table 5.4b shows the majority of the respondents prefer to invest for their safety measures, followed by reducing their tax liability and medical expenditure.

Suggestions

- Home makers should give priority for long term investment.
- Home makers should have a list of their financial goals and they should set timeframe for reaching each one.
- Homemakers should decide whether they have to take investment decision on their own or to get assistance from others. If they get assistance from others, they should help the homemakers to reach the right level of progress.
- Home makers should at least have a quarterly update and should track their progress.
- The financial institution need to come up with more serious focus, workshops, and demonstrations to shape women's confidence and financial decision making skills
- It can also be concluded that home makers are more serious in making investment than the unmarried ones as they believe they have a sense of responsibility towards their family and children.
- The government, Bankers and Financial institutions can introduce lot of schemes of investment based on segmentation of the age and marital status factors to acquire more funds.
- This study will help the financial institutions in designing exclusive instruments for women and to the Government in coming up with new policies for utilizing women's savings for the betterment of the Indian economy

IV. CONCLUSION

There are number of investment options are avail for the investors. While making investments the investors must consider such factors as return and safety of funds. In this study the researcher has attempted to study the preference of investors, investment patterns, problem faced by the investors and their level awareness on investment. Women investors don't have throw knowledge of all the investment avenues and they don't want to take risk. Women are not able to take independent decision and mostly rely on others for their own investment decision. Women should be encouraged to invest in more avenues and should participate in the investment which involves high risk and also high return. Women should focus making a formal financial plan and they should invest in their investment.

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